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Ballinacourty House Caravan and Camping Park representing the historical Ballinacourty House

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reviewed by Eugen Unterberger

Ballinacourty House traces its origins back to the English Civil Wars between 1642 and 1651. During this period, Oliver Cromwell ‘borrowed’ money from so-called ‘adventurers’, who were granted land in return. This is how John Dawson came into possession of Ballinacourty in Aherlow. He had Ballinacourty House built on the land in 1663 and took up residence there. His descendants, the Dawson family, and through marriage also the Massy and Sanders families, preserved Ballinacourty House for almost three centuries and provided employment for local people. Following the passing of the first Land Law Ireland Act, the estate was acquired by its then residents, only to be burned down by the Anti-Treaty Irish Republican Army during the Irish Civil War in 1922/23, ironically, as both its origins and its destruction were shaped by civil wars. Compensation enabled the construction of a new estate, which served as a hotel until parts of it were converted into what is now Ballinacourty House Caravan and Camping Park. Several walls from the older buildings that were part of the estate still remain today.

Visitors to Ballinacourty House Caravan and Camping Park only perceive the living history of this place at second glance. They usually find the campsite on the Internet, in travel guides, or in relevant campsite listings. They drive there, check in, and spent the night. Although the nearby house, built after the original Ballinacourty House was destroyed during the Irish Civil War in 1922/23, has some history of its own, this alone is not enough to set it apart from the many other old buildings in the area. The rich history of the place is only revealed through the information sheet displayed at the campsite reception, which informs visitors about the history of Ballinacourty

House, and through the verbal explanations provided by the campsite owner. These explanations embed the present-day campsite within its historical context. Her lively voice, enthusiasm, and skilful storytelling create an emotional connection between the present and the past. Although this process forms part of the current place-making, it is primarily intended as a representation of history.

Within the old walls of the estate, the owner has created a secret garden. The walls are historical and dilapidated, as is evident, for example, from the signs of decay caused by weathering. Since the secret garden adapts to the historical layout of the estate, in particular, by incorporating the walls into its design, it is at least partly a product of times gone by. Yet, it also forms part of contemporary history and the present day, not least because a garden requires constant maintenance. As the old walls are in this way linked to the present place and the garden’s design reflects the former one, the two places become mutually connected. This experience of the historicity of the place is complemented by sensory experiences. Many of the flowers and plants in the secret garden display rich, highly saturated colours and exude an intense, fresh fragrance. Not only are the numerous plants beautiful in themselves, but so is the way in which they combine to form a whole. This sensual richness and splendour of colours serve as a metaphor for the vibrant history that this place has undergone, and one senses that this history has not yet come to an end but continues to be actively lived. In this sense, the secret garden, including its walls, are witnesses to the living history of this place.

The information sheet, the oral explanations, the secret garden, and the walls each refer to the history of the place and Ballinacourty House, but only in combination do they unfold their effect. Every place has its history, because it is created through processes of place-making, and even its creation assumes a period of time. Although the temporal and causal connection between the past and the present place establishes the affordance of the present place to represent the past place, and vice versa, this affordance is not realized in many cases. In the case of Ballinacourty House, however, the owner's awareness of, appreciation for, and enthusiasm about this connection lead to a variety of genuinely experienceable references to the past place. By understanding the present place as a temporal extension of the past place and its history, the lived experience of the present place transcends to the past one, making the former a lived representation of the latter.